

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula	λ_{\max} nm
1.	H	147	60	Light yellow	$C_{17}H_{16}N_6$	240, 350
2.	2'-NO ₂	195	70	Yellow	$C_{17}H_{15}N_7O_2$	250, 390
3.	3'-NO ₂	300d	75	Brown	$C_{17}H_{15}N_7O_2$	255, 370
4.	4'-NO ₂	200d	65	Yellow	$C_{17}H_{15}N_7O_2$	240, 390
5.	2'-Cl	150	60	Yellow	$C_{17}H_{15}N_6Cl$	250, 380
6.	3'-Cl	130	63	Yellow	$C_{17}H_{15}N_6Cl$	250, 380
7.	4'-Cl	170	60	Yellow	$C_{17}H_{15}N_6Cl$	250, 360
8.	2'-CH ₃	155	69	Yellow	$C_{18}H_{19}N_6$	245, 255
9.	3'-CH ₃	137	70	Orange	$C_{18}H_{19}N_6$	240, 350
10.	4'-CH ₃	110	75	Brown	$C_{18}H_{19}N_6$	240, 390
11.	2',5'-(Cl) ₂	172	75	Light yellow	$C_{17}H_{14}N_6Cl_2$	250, 360
12.	2',3'-(CH ₃) ₂	130	68	Orange	$C_{19}H_{20}N_6$	250, 360
13.	2',5'-(CH ₃) ₂	170	63	Yellow	$C_{19}H_{20}N_6$	240, 350
14.	4'-OCH ₃	230	69	Yellow	$C_{18}H_{19}N_6O$	250, 380
15.	3'-OCH ₃	180	61	Brown	$C_{18}H_{19}N_6O$	260, 350
16.	2'-OC ₂ H ₅	125	67	Yellow	$C_{19}H_{20}N_6O$	250, 400
17.	4'-COOH	290	70	Yellow	$C_{18}H_{16}N_6O_2$	260, 385
18.	3'-NO ₂ , 4'-OH ₂	105	67	Blackish brown	$C_{18}H_{16}N_7O_2$	250, 360

*All compounds gave consistent C, H and N analyses.

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Nucleophilic Addition-Elimination Reactions of 2-Hydrazinobenzothiazoles with Indolin-2,3-diones

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It has been observed that 2-aminobenzothiazoles do not undergo nucleophilic addition-elimination reactions with indolin-2,3-diones due to poor nucleophilicity of amino group. However, the moment 2-amino group is replaced with 2-hydrazino group, the reaction takes place with ease. In the present communication, we report nucleophilic reactions of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles¹ with

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indolin-2,3-dione^a and several 5-substituted-2,3-diones^b. Thus 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles on treatment with indolin-2,3-diones under mild acidic

conditions gave **2** in nearly quantitative yields. When 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles were allowed to react with 1-methyl-5-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones^c, under similar conditions, compounds **3** were obtained in good yields. Compounds **2** were further subjected to Mannich reaction whereby the corresponding 1-morpholinomethyl analogs were obtained. The structural assignments of the compounds are based on elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded

on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl_3) using TMS as an internal standard at 90 MHz and mass spectra at 70 eV.

3-(6-Substituted-2-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-5-substituted-2-indolinones (2): To a suspension of 6-substituted-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.01 mol) and 5-substituted-isatin (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath, resulting in a complete dissolution of the reactants. The refluxing was continued for 2 h and the solid that separated was filtered under suction, washed repeatedly with methanol and air-dried (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL* DATA OF COMPOUNDS**

	R	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	H	Cl	>260	60	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
2b	Cl	Me	>275	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
2c	Me	Cl	>240	63	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
2d	H	Me	>250	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
2e	H	OMe	>240	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S
2f	Me	OMe	>240	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S
2g	Me	Me	>260	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S
2h	Cl	Cl	>260	68	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
2i	Cl	OMe	>260	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3a	Cl	OMe	260	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₃ S
3b	Me	Cl	240	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
3c	Cl	Cl	260	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
3d	Me	Me	235	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S
3e	H	Me	220	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S
3f	H	OMe	230	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S
3g	Cl	Me	245	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
3h	Me	OMe	236	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ S
3i	H	Cl	246	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
4a	Me	Cl	210	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
4b	H	Me	186	68	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ S
4c	H	OMe	205	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₃ S
4d	Me	OMe	203	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃ S
4e	Me	Me	198	75	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ S
4f	Cl	Cl	210	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
4g	Cl	OMe	232	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ ClN ₄ O ₃ S

Compounds **2 could not be crystallised due to their insolubility in common organic solvents, they were therefore analysed as morpholinomethyl analogs (**3**); satisfactory C, H analyses were obtained for compounds **3** and **4**.

* ν_{max} **2d** 1 700 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N); **2e** 1 700 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N); **2h** 1 690 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N); **2i** 1 690 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N); **3e** 1 670 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N); **3h** 1 690 (C=O), 1 605 (C=N); **3a** m/z 372/374, **3b** 356/358, **3c** 376/378, **3g** 356/358, **3i** 341/344; δ **4a** 2.39 (s, OH₂), 2.65 (t, N(CH₂)₂), 3.7: (t, O(CH₂)₂), 4.45 (s, N-OH₂N), 6.8-7.6 (ArH, NH); **4b** 2.44 (s, Me), 2.6 (t, N(CH₂)₂), 3.7 (t, O(CH₂)₂), 4.5 (s, N-CH₂-N), 7-7.7 (m, ArH, NH), **4c** 2.7 (t, N(CH₂)₂), 3.73 (t, O(CH₂)₂), 3.86 (s, OCH₃), 4.53 (s, N-CH₂-N), 6.9-7.7 (m, ArH, NH).

3-(6-Substituted-2-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-5-substituted-1-methyl-2-indolinones (3): To 6-substituted-2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (0.01 mol) and 1-methyl-5-substituted-isatin (0.01 mol) taken in methanol (20 ml), was added glacial acetic acid (3-4 drops). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The reactants dissolved followed by the separation of the solid product. The solid was filtered under suction and washed with methanol several times and recrystallised from DMF-water (Table 1).

3-(6-Substituted-2-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-5-substituted-1-morpholinomethyl-2-indolinones (4): To 3-(6-substituted-2-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-5-substituted-2-indolinone (0.005 mol) suspended in hot DMF (20.0 ml), were added 40% formaldehyde (0.5 ml) and morpholine (0.5 ml) and the reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath till a clear solution resulted. The solid product separated on keeping the solution overnight, was filtered under suction, washed several times with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (Table 1).

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A Few 2-(Substituted-acetyl)-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles as CNS Depressants

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COMPOUNDS containing 1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus have been reported to possess various biological activities¹, when properly substituted at 2- or 5-position of the ring.

In continuation of our earlier work on 1,3,4-thiadiazoles as CNS depressants², the title compounds were prepared and evaluated for CNS depressant activity. Condensation of thiosemicarbazide (1) with aliphatic acid in presence of sulphuric acid gave 2-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2). Acetylation of 2 with chloroacetyl chloride and condensation with the appropriate amine yielded 2-(substituted-acetyl)amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (4).

All the compounds showed characteristic IR bands at 3 450–3 300 (NH), 1 700–1 680 (C=O), 1 210, 1 075, 980 and 825 cm^{-1} (1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus).

Experimental

All the compounds were routinely checked by tlc on silica gel-G using ethanol-acetic acid-water (5 : 3 : 2) for purity. IR spectra (KBr) of compounds were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. The melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected.

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2) : The compounds were prepared³ using thiosemicarbazide (1; 0.125 mol), aliphatic acid (0.150 mol) and concentrated sulphuric acid (25 ml) : 2a (R = methyl) (65%), m.p. 228–30° (lit. 230°), yield 65%; 2b (R = ethyl) (80%), 192–94° (lit. 194°); 2c (R = propyl) (80%) 202–04° (lit. 204°).

2-Chloroacetylamino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3) : To compound 2 (0.10 mol) dissolved in dioxane (25 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.10 mol) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h. On adding the mixture to ice-cold distilled water, a solid product was obtained which was recrystallisation from ethanol (95%, v/v) : 3a (R = methyl) (90%), m.p. 235–36° (lit. 236°); 3b (R = ethyl) (80%), 224–26° (lit. 226°); 3c (R = propyl) (85%) 206–08° (lit. 208°).

2-(Substituted-acetyl)amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4) : A mixture of 3 (0.02 mol), appropriate amine (0.04–0.05 mol) and benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 4–5 h. The amine hydrochloride which crystallised out on cooling was filtered off. The filtrate was extracted several times with hydrochloric acid (1N). The combined acid extracts were made alkaline with sodium hydroxide (1N) and extracted with diethyl ether several times. The ether extracts were combined and the solvent distilled off to get crude product which was recrystallised from ethanol (90%, v/v) (Table 1).

Biological studies : The drug solutions (100 mg ml^{-1}) of the compounds were prepared in normal saline. The approximate lethal dose (ALD_{50}) was determined in mice intraperitoneally (i.p.) by the reported method⁴. The effect on gross behaviour pattern, response to touch, pain and sound, sedation,